

ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF REPLACEMENT OF WHEAT RESIDUES IN PLASTER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work was to evaluate the influence of different levels of wheat residue substitution (0.00 %, 2.50 %, 5.00 %, 7.50 % and 10.00 %) on the mechanical properties of plaster composites. For this, the wheat residues were pre-prepared and incorporated into plaster composites with dimensions of 40.00x40.00x160.00 mm and cured for 7 days. The composites were characterized by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), bending and compression. Preliminary results showed that composites with higher amounts of wheat fibers exhibited a decrease in their mechanical properties and a more porous surface.

KEYWORDS

Vegetable fibers; agricultural waste; low environmental impact products.

INTRODUCTION

Composites are made by mixing two or more materials. In this way, a third product with improved properties is developed. Gypsum is an example of a commonly used composite. The growth in the consumption of this material is due to the excellent finish it provides to surfaces and the ease of molding, which makes it widely used in coatings, linings, boards, and pre-molded ornaments. Although this material is fire resistant, has excellent thermal and acoustic properties, does not shrink after drying, and has an excellent surface finish, it has some limitations such as high-water permeability, high porosity, low flexural and tensile strength, and low compression strength, which restrict its applications to indoor environments. Most economic processes mainly related to composites generated in the construction industry, such as gypsum, have a severe impact on the environment, causing soil and groundwater contamination (Vilela *et al.*, 2020; Veloso *et al.*, 2021).

Therefore, the civil construction industry is in constant search for the development of materials with less input of primary raw material. In this context, composite materials with the presence of lignocellulosic residues stand out, which improves the properties of the final product and contributes to the preservation of the environment (Oliveira *et al.*, 2020).

Lignocellulosic residues from the Brazilian agroindustry are still abundant, renewable, biodegradable, have low density, low elastic modulus, high tensile strength and are highly available, hence exhibiting great potential to be used as reinforcement in composite materials. One of the most common lignocellulosic residues is those obtained from plant fibers, used as they present good chemical, physical and mechanical characteristics (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2018; Veloso *et al.*, 2021).

Studies related to the use of gypsum as a ceramic matrix for the manufacture of composites have been developed incorporating different materials such as cellulosic pulp, wood particles and industrial waste.

Among the restudies some fibers stand out for this purpose jute, sisal, coconut, bamboo and wheat (Almeida *et al.*, 2010; Oliveira *et al.*, 2012; Mesquita, 2013).

From these, wheat fibers residue could be used for forming a composite material. This agricultural product is one of the most cultivated cereals and is part of the composition of several products, present on the consumer's table, such as pasta, bread, and cookies. Brazil is one of the major producers of wheat and in 2020 alone, it was responsible for the production of about 6.20 million tons of this cereal, equivalent to 54.00 % of national consumption. However, the processing of this grain is responsible for a large generation of waste, which, if not properly disposed of, can cause damage to the environment (CONAB, 2020).

In this context, the aim of this work was to evaluate the influence of the substitution of different levels of wheat residues (0.00 %, 2.50 %, 5.00 %, 7.50 %, and 10.00 %) on the mechanical properties of plaster-based composites.

METHODOLOGY

Wheat (*Triticum spp.*) residues were collected at the Experimental Farm of the Universidade Federal de Lavras (UFLA), in the city of Ijaci / Minas Gerais / Brazil. Gypsum, on the other hand, was obtained from the local market in the city of Lavras / Minas Gerais / Brazil and met the specifications of the EN 14496 (CEN, 2017).

To obtain the wheat particles, a high rotation hammer mill, brand Lucato (Limeira, São Paulo, Brazil), was used. The particle size distribution was evaluated by the sieving method, using the A Bronzinox sieve (São Paulo, Brazil). For the production of composites, the particles passing through the 20 mesh sieve and retained on the 40 mesh sieve were used.

After the preparing process of the lignocellulosic residue, the composites production stage was initiated. The treatments performed (Table 1) were based on the work developed by Oliveira *et al.* (2010). For each treatment, six specimens with dimensions of 40.00x40.00x160.00 mm were produced, according to the specifications of EN 13279-2 (CEN, 2014).

Table 1: Treatments used in this research.

Treatments	Plaster (%)	Wheat waste (%)
T1	100.00	0.00
T2	97.50	2.50
T3	95.00	5.00
T4	92.50	7.50
T5	90.00	10.00

For the production of composites, a water/gypsum ratio of 0.6 was used, as it provides better workability to the mixture, even after the addition of waste (Oliveira *et al.*, 2020). After making, the specimens underwent a curing process for 7 days. Then, they were demolded and stored in a ventilated place, free from bad weather. Subsequently, they were cut to determine their mechanical properties.

The influence of wheat residue replacement in gypsum composites was evaluated through mechanical compression and bending tests - EN 13279-2 (CEN, 2014), to determine the Modulus of Elasticity (MOE) and Modulus of Rupture (MOR) in both tests.

To evaluate the interaction between the gypsum and wheat particles, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was also performed on the specimens ruptured in static bending. For this purpose, a SEM Zeiss EVO 40 microscope (Oberkochen, Baden - Württemberg, Germany) operated at a voltage of 15.00 kV and a probe current of 2.00 nA was used. All samples from this analysis were coated with gold. The

analysis took place at the Laboratory of Microscopy, Department of Plant Pathology, UFLA. Secondary electrons and backscatter detectors were used at a working distance of 8.50 mm and without inclination to carry out this test.

Finally, to verify the effects of treatments on the quality of the panels, a completely randomized design was adopted. The data of the analyzed properties were submitted to linear regression, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and also to Tukey's test at 5.00 % probability, to compare the means.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flexural and compressive strength

The results of Modulus of Elasticity (MOE) and Modulus of Rupture (MOR), derived from the flexural strength, are represented in Figure 1, exhibiting similar behaviour between each other, those specimens without the addition of reinforcement material presented greater flexural strength, and with an increasing percentage of reinforcement, the strength progressively decreases. This decrease may probably occur due to the action of the density of wheat fibers, which is low, inferior to that of gypsum, and which has a great influence on the mechanical strength of the material. These results are related to what was exposed by Oliveira *et al.* (2020), which uses multilayer packaging crushed in a gypsum matrix, and similarly, according to Veloso *et al.* (2021) when using cocoa residues, the low values presented can also mean poor adhesion between the wheat fibers and the gypsum.

* Significant regression analysis at 5.00 % significance.

Figure 1: Modulus of Elasticity (MOE) (a) and Modulus of Rupture (MOR) (b) of flexural strength.

The values of MOE flexural strength of the composites ranged from 227.56 MPa to 54.16 MPa and those of MOR from 3.64 MPa to 1.26 MPa, with a statistically significant difference between them and the highest value in both cases being that without the addition of fibers (0.00 %). Contrary to what was exposed by Silva Oliveira *et al.* (2020), who use eucalyptus wood fibers as reinforcement and whose flexural strength tends to increase, thus, for example, MOR values increased as the fiber addition percentage increases (2.50 % to 10.00 %). However, all composites incorporating fibers into the gypsum matrix met the EN 13279-1 (CEN, 2014) requirement of 1.00 MPa for flexural strength.

Regarding the results of MOE and MOR of the compressive strength of the composites shown in Figure 2, values varied from 163.74 MPa to 802.05 MPa and from 3.35 MPa to 10.24 MPa, respectively, being the highest value the composite without the addition of reinforcement fibers, the same trend as the results obtained in the bending tests.

* Significant regression analysis at 5.00 % significance.

Figure 2: Modulus of Elasticity (MOE) (a) and Modulus of Rupture (MOR) (b) of the compressive strength of composites.

In the compression test, it was observed that the MOE of the material with 2.50 % replacement of gypsum by wheat fibers was higher than the other percentages of incorporation, therefore, it can be considered as the maximum limit for the addition of this type of reinforcements for the material. Likewise, in relation to MOR, the treatments were statistically identical from the addition of 5.00 % to 10.00 % of the fibers (Tukey's tests with 5.00 % of significance), and the one with the highest value remained to be the one without the reinforcement addition.

On the contrary, with what has been exposed in the literature, Tichi *et al.* (2020), and Rangavar *et al.* (2016), showed that the abundance of extractives in lignocellulosic materials has been shown to reduce the hydration of gypsum, and increase the retention of these materials in the matrix. However, in the present study, the retention of wheat fibers in the gypsum composite was not optimal, possibly due to the porosity of the material, which can negatively influence the bond strength of the reinforcement in the matrix (Veloso *et al.*, 2021). What is more, all composites produced exceeded the minimum value of 2.00 MPa required by the EN 13279-1 (CEN, 2014) standard for the compressive strength of gypsum.

Microstructure of composites

The images in Figure 3, show the Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) micrographs of the composites without reinforcement and incorporated with different percentages of wheat fibers, after static bending. In the reference composite (Figure 3a), it can be observed gypsum crystals, typical of the gypsum crystalline morphology and no visible pores in its surface (Oliveira *et al.*, 2020; Vimrová *et al.*, 2011; Carvalho *et al.*, 2008).

a) without reinforcements

b) 2.50 % of wheat fibers

c) 5.00 % of wheat fibers

b) 7.50 % of wheat fibers

e) 10.00 % of wheat fibers

Figure 3: SEM images.

For the composites produced with fiber reinforcement (Figure 3b, c, d, e) the presence of voids was observed, verifying that the fibers were not uniformly dispersed in the gypsum matrix and that there was not an optimal bonding between the wheat fibers and gypsum (Figure 3b), in addition, no pores filling was observed and this absence may have caused the large cavities observed (Figure 3d, e) which can mean a reduction in the dimensional stability and density of the composites (Villela *et al.*, 2020; Tichi *et al.*, 2020).

CONCLUSION

The present work aimed to evaluate different levels of substitution of wheat residues (*Triticum spp.*) in the properties of plaster composites as a reinforcement alternative to this material of great environmental and economic interest. Among the conclusions of the work carried out, it can be mentioned that:

- Mechanical properties were significantly affected by the presence of lignocellulosic material, resulting in a decrease concomitant with higher levels of gypsum replacement by wheat residues;
- On the other hand, all specimens complied with the regulations regarding the Modulus of Rupture (MOR), both in the bending and compression tests;
- Regarding the images obtained by the microscope of specimens broken in static bending, a large presence of voids was observed, verifying that the fibers were not uniformly dispersed in the plaster matrix and that there was not an optimal bonding between the wheat fibers and gypsum, which may explain the low mechanical performance of these composites.

Therefore, such preliminary results point to the unfeasibility of producing these composites on a large scale in civil construction.

Further research is recommended, however, to know the other properties of these components (physical, chemical, thermal, etc.). In these new researches, the use of pre-treatments in the particles of wheat residues could also be analyzed in order to improve the main problem found in this research, its large number of voids.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

1. Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.